

Task 1 (40 pts)

UML class diagram solution

General UML diagram syntax

1. Did not correctly mark fields as *private* using the minus sign. -1 pt

Deduct -1 pt per occurrence, up to -2 pts maximum deduction.

2. Did not correctly list a field with its name followed by its type. -1 pt

Deduct -1 pt per occurrence, up to -2 pts maximum deduction.

When specifying a field, the name of the field should be followed by a colon and then its type.

3. Did not correctly mark methods as *public* using the plus sign. -1 pt

Deduct -1 pt per occurrence, up to -2 pts maximum deduction.

4. Did not correctly list a method with parameters and types (if any), and the return type of the method itself. -1 pt

Deduct -1 pt per occurrence, up to -2 pts maximum deduction.

When specifying a method, the name of the method should be followed in parentheses by the parameters that the method accepts with their types (if any), followed by a colon and then the return type.

5. Incorrectly included an inherited field in the class diagram of a derived class. -1 pt

Deduct -1 pt per occurrence, up to -2 pts maximum deduction.

Fields that are inherited from a base class should not be listed in the class diagram of the derived class. For example, the name field in the Assessment class should not be listed again in, say, the TopHatQuestion class.

Top-level base class

1. Did not correctly include a top-level base class that contains the fields that all classes will inherit. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is Assessment. However, students could have used a different name for this top-level base class.

2. Did not correctly include two fields: 1) name of type String and 2) fullScore of type int. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

3. Incorrectly included the field numberOfProblems in this class. -1 pt

Only deduct once here, i.e., don't deduct again if the field is not included in the derived classes.

Students may have included the numberOfProblems field in this base class because challenge activities, participation activities, programming assignments, and exams all have this field. However, TopHat questions do not have this field. Therefore, the field should remain in the classes that require it (i.e., in the ZyBookActivity, ProgrammingAssignment, and Exam classes).

Class for a TopHat question

1. Did not correctly include a class to represent a TopHat question. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is TopHatQuestion. However, students could have used a different name, but should use a name that is somehow related to TopHat questions.

2. Did not correctly specify that this class is a derived class of the Assessment top-level base class using an arrow pointing to the top-level base class. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the TopHatQuestion class is designated as a derived class of the Assessment base class with an arrow from the TopHatQuestion class to the Assessment class.

3. Did not correctly include two fields: 1) topic of type String and 2) participationCount of type int. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

4. Did not correctly include a getPercentage method that accepts a double as a parameter and returns a double. -1 pt

Students can use a different name for the parameter, i.e., the parameter name does not have to be score.

5. Did not correctly include an overloaded getPercentage method that accepts an int as a parameter and returns a double. -1 pt

Students can use a different name for the parameter, i.e., the parameter name does not have to be totalEnrollment.

6. Did not correctly include a toString method. -1 pt

This method should not accept any parameters and should return a String.

Base class for zyBooks activities

1. Did not correctly include a base class that contains the fields that classes for challenge and participation activities will inherit. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is ZyBookActivity. However, students could have used a different name for this base level class.

2. Did not correctly specify that this class is a derived class of the Assessment top-level base class using an arrow pointing to the top-level base class. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the ZyBookActivity class is designated as a derived class of the Assessment base class with an arrow from the ZyBookActivity class to the Assessment class.

3. Did not correctly include two fields: 1) chapter and 2) numberOfProblems, both of type int. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

4. Did not correctly include a toString method. -1 pt

This method should not accept any parameters and should return a String.

Class for a zyBooks challenge activity

1. Did not correctly include a class to represent a zyBook challenge activity. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is ChallengeActivity. However, students could have used a different name, but should use a name that is somehow related to zyBooks challenge activities.

2. Did not correctly include specifying that this class is a derived class of the ZyBookActivity base class using an arrow pointing to the base class. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the ChallengeActivity class is designated as a derived class of the ZyBookActivity base class with an arrow from the ChallengeActivity class to the ZyBookActivity class.

3. Did not correctly include two fields: 1) hasCoding and 2) hasStepThrough, both of type boolean. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

4. Did not correctly include a toString method. -1 pt

This method should not accept any parameters and should return a String.

Class for a zyBooks participation activity

1. Did not correctly include a class to represent a zyBook participation activity. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is ParticipationActivity. However, students could have used a different name, but should use a name that is somehow related to zyBooks participation activities.

2. Did not correctly include specify that this class is a derived class of the ZyBookActivity base class using an arrow pointing to the base class. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the ParticipationActivity class is designated as a derived class of the ZyBookActivity base class with an arrow from the ParticipationActivity class to the ZyBookActivity class.

3. Did not correctly include three fields: 1) hasTrueFalse, 2) hasMultipleChoice, and 3) hasAnimation, all three of type boolean. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

4. Did not correctly include a toString method. -1 pt

This method should not accept any parameters and should return a String.

Class for a programming assignment

1. Did not correctly include a class to represent a programming assignment. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is ProgrammingAssignment. However, students could have used a different name, but should use a name that is somehow related to programming assignments.

2. Did not correctly include specify that this class is a derived class of the Assessment top-level base class using an arrow pointing to the top-level base class. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the ProgrammingAssignment class is designated as a derived class of the Assessment base class with an arrow from the ProgrammingAssignment class to the Assessment class.

3. Did not correctly include two fields: 1) numberOfProblems of type int and 2) hasWarmup of type boolean. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

4. Did not correctly include a toString method. -1 pt

This method should not accept any parameters and should return a String.

Class for an exam

1. Did not correctly include a class to represent an exam. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is Exam. However, students could have used a different name, but should use a name that is somehow related to exams.

2. Did not correctly specify that this class is a derived class of the Assessment top-level base class using an arrow pointing to the top-level base class. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the Exam class is designated as a derived class of the Assessment base class with an arrow from the Exam class to the Assessment class.

3. Did not correctly include one field: numberOfProblems of type int. -1 pt

The field name and type must be as specified.

4. Did not correctly include a toString method. -1 pt

This method should not accept any parameters and should return a String.

Class for a final exam

1. Did not correctly include a class to represent a final exam. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is FinalExam. However, students could have used a different name, but should use a name that is somehow related to final exams.

2. Did not correctly include specify that this class is a derived class of the Exam base class using an arrow pointing to the base class. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the FinalExam class is designated as a derived class of the Exam base class with an arrow from the FinalExam class to the Exam class.

3. Did not correctly include three fields: 1) preExam1Topics, 2) preExam2Topics, and 3) preFinalExamTopics, all three of type int. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

4. Did not correctly include a toString method. -1 pt

This method should not accept any parameters and should return a String.

Task 2 (40 pts)

Note – For this task, the methods do not need to be implemented. That is, the toString methods in the classes below could simply return an empty string.

The expected solution for **Question No. 3** of the **Post-evaluation Survey** (i.e., the toString method implementations) can be seen in class implementations below.

Java class solutions

```
public class Assessment {
    private String name;
    private int fullScore;

    public String toString() {
        return "Name: " + name + "\n" +
            "Full score: " + fullScore + "\n";
    }
}
```

```
public class TopHatQuestion extends Assessment {
    private String topic;
    private int participationCount;

    public double getPercentage(double score) {
        return 0.0;
    }

    public double getPercentage(int totalEnrollment) {
        return 0.0;
    }

    public String toString() {
        return super.toString() + "\n" +
            "Topic of question: " + topic + "\n" +
            "Number of students who participated: " + participationCount + "\n";
    }
}
```

```
public class ZyBookActivity extends Assessment {
    private int chapter;
    private int numberOfProblems;

    public String toString() {
        return super.toString() +
            "Chapter: " + chapter + "\n" +
            "Number of problems: " + numberOfProblems + "\n";
    }
}
```

```
public class ChallengeActivity extends ZyBookActivity {
    private boolean hasCoding;
    private boolean hasStepThrough;

    public String toString() {
        String str = super.toString();

        if (hasCoding) {
            str += "- Has coding problem(s)" + "\n";
        } else {
            str += "- No coding problem(s)" + "\n";
        }

        if (hasStepThrough) {
            str += "- Has code step-through problem(s)" + "\n";
        } else {
            str += "- No code step-through problem(s)" + "\n";
        }

        return str;
    }
}
```

```
public class ParticipationActivity extends ZyBookActivity {
    private boolean hasTrueFalse;
    private boolean hasMultipleChoice;
    private boolean hasAnimation;

    public String toString() {
        String str = super.toString();

        if (hasTrueFalse) {
            str += "- Has true or false question(s)" + "\n";
        } else {
            str += "- No true or false question(s)" + "\n";
        }

        if (hasMultipleChoice) {
            str += "- Has multiple choice question(s)" + "\n";
        } else {
            str += "- No multiple choice question(s)" + "\n";
        }

        if (hasAnimation) {
            str += "- Has animation" + "\n";
        } else {
            str += "- No animation" + "\n";
        }

        return str;
    }
}
```

```
public class ProgrammingAssignment extends Assessment {
    private int numberOfProblems;
    private boolean hasWarmup;

    public String toString() {
        String str = super.toString();

        str += "Number of problems: " + numberOfProblems + "\n";

        if (hasWarmup) {
            str += "- Has warmup problem(s)" + "\n";
        } else {
            str += "- No warmup problem(s)" + "\n";
        }

        return str;
    }
}
```

```
public class Exam extends Assessment {
    private int numberOfProblems;

    public String toString() {
        return super.toString() + "\n" +
            "Number of problems: " + numberOfProblems + "\n";
    }
}
```

```
public class FinalExam extends Exam {
    private int preExam1Topics;
    private int preExam2Topics;
    private int preFinalExamTopics;

    public String toString() {
        return super.toString() + "\n" +
            "Topics before Exam 1: " + preExam1Topics + "%\n" +
            "Topics before Exam 2: " + preExam2Topics + "%\n" +
            "Topics before Final Exam: " + preFinalExamTopics + "%\n";
    }
}
```

It is likely that if the student was correct in the UML class diagram, they will also be correct in the Java class implementation. But if that is not the case, then deduct accordingly (i.e., if correct in the UML class diagram, but not correct in the Java class implementation, deduct for the Java code implementation, and vice versa). In contrast, if the solution is not correct in both the UML class diagram and the Java class implementation, then deduct twice for both tasks.

General Java class requirements

1. Did not correctly specify the fields as `private`. -1 pt

Deduct -1 pt per occurrence, up to -2 pts maximum deduction.

2. Did not correctly specify the methods as `public`. -1 pt

Deduct -1 pt per occurrence, up to -2 pts maximum deduction.

3. Incorrectly included an inherited field in the class diagram of a derived class. -1 pt

Deduct -1 pt per occurrence, up to -2 pts maximum deduction.

Fields that are inherited from a base class should not be listed in the class diagram of the derived class. For example, the name field in the Assessment class should not be listed again in, say, the TopHatQuestion class.

Top-level base class

1. Did not correctly include a top-level base class that will contain the fields that all classes will inherit. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is Assessment. However, students could have used a different name for this top-level base class.

2. Did not correctly include two fields: 1) name of type `String` and 2) `fullScore` of type `int`. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

3. Incorrectly included the field `numberOfProblems` in this class. -1 pt

Only deduct once here, i.e., don't deduct again if the field is not included in the derived classes.

Students may include the numberOfProblems field in this base class because challenge activities, participation activities, programming assignments, and exams all have this field. However, TopHat questions do not have this field. Therefore, the field should remain in the classes that require it (i.e., in the ZyBookActivity, ProgrammingAssignment, and Exam classes).

Class for a TopHat question

1. Did not correctly include a class to represent a TopHat question. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is TopHatQuestion. However, students could have used a different name, but should use a name that is somehow related to TopHat questions.

2. Did not correctly include specify that this class extends the Assessment top-level base class. -1 pt
-

3. Did not correctly include two fields: 1) topic of type String and 2) participationCount of type int. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

4. Did not correctly include a getPercentage method that accepts a double as a parameter and returns a double. -1 pt

Students can use a different name for the parameter, i.e., the parameter name does not have to be score. It is okay if the value returned is zero.

5. Did not correctly include an overloaded getPercentage method that accepts an int as a parameter and returns a double. -1 pt

Students can use a different name for the parameter, i.e., the parameter name does not have to be totalEnrollment. It is okay if the value returned is zero.

6. Did not correctly include a toString method. -1 pt

This method should not accept any parameters and should return a String. It is okay if the value returned is an empty string.

Base class for zyBooks activities

1. Did not correctly include a base class that contains the fields that classes for challenge and participation activities will inherit. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is ZyBookActivity. However, students could have used a different name for this base level class.

2. Did not correctly include specify that this class extends the Assessment top-level base class.
-

3. Did not correctly include two fields: 1) chapter and 2) numberOfProblems, both of type int. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

4. Did not correctly include a toString method. -1 pt

This method should not accept any parameters and should return a String. It is okay if the value returned is an empty string.

Class for a zyBooks challenge activity

1. Did not correctly include a class to represent a zyBook challenge activity. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is ChallengeActivity. However, students could have used a different name, but should use a name that is somehow related to zyBooks challenge activities.

2. Did not correctly specify that this class extends the ZyBookActivity base class. -1 pt
-

3. Did not correctly include two fields: 1) hasCoding and 2) hasStepThrough, both of type boolean. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

4. Inclusion of the toString method in the class. -1 pt

This method should not accept any parameters and should return a String. It is okay if the value returned is an empty string.

Class for a zyBooks participation activity

1. Did not correctly include a class to represent a zyBook participation activity. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is ParticipiationActivity. However, students could have used a different name, but should use a name that is somehow related to zyBooks participation activities.

2. Did not correctly specify that this class extends the ZyBookActivity base class. -1 pt
-

3. Did not correctly include three fields: 1) hasTrueFalse, 2) hasMultipleChoice, and 3) hasAnimation, all three of type boolean. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

4. Inclusion of the toString method in the class. -1 pt

This method should not accept any parameters and should return a String. It is okay if the value returned is an empty string.

Class for a programming assignment

1. Did not correctly include a class to represent a programming assignment. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is ProgrammingAssignment. However, students could have used a different name, but should use a name that is somehow related to programming assignments.

2. Did not correctly specify that this class extends the Assessment top-level base class. -1 pt
-

3. Did not correctly include two fields in the class: 1) numberOfProblems of type int and 2) hasWarmup of type boolean. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

4. Inclusion of the toString method in the class. -1 pt

This method should not accept any parameters and should return a String. It is okay if the value returned is an empty string.

Class for an exam

1. Did not correctly include a class to represent an exam. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is Exam. However, students could have used a different name, but should use a name that is somehow related to exams.

2. Did not correctly specify that this class extends the Assessment top-level base class. -1 pt
-

3. Did not correctly include one field: numberOfProblems of type int. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

4. Inclusion of the toString method in the class. -1 pt

This method should not accept any parameters and should return a String. It is okay if the value returned is an empty string.

Class for a final exam

1. Did not correctly include a class to represent a final exam. -1 pt

In the provided solution, the name of this is FinalExam. However, students could have used a different name, but should use a name that is somehow related to final exams.

2. Did not correctly specify that this class extends the Exam base class. -1 pt

3. Did not correctly include three fields: 1) preExam1Topics, 2) preExam2Topics, and 3) preFinalExamTopics, all three of type int. -1 pt

The field names and types must be as specified.

4. Inclusion of the toString method in the class. -1 pt

This method should not accept any parameters and should return a String. It is okay if the value returned is an empty string.
